

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

10
2023

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
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74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

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Elektron nashr. 692 sahifa, 30-oktyabr, 2023-yil.

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Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

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ANALYSING THE FUNCTIONING OF ENTERPRISE MANAGEMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF INSTITUTIONAL REFORMS

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Abstract: The article considers the main problems of functioning of enterprises in the conditions of transformation of the national economy of Uzbekistan. The functions performed by enterprises in the society are defined. The author identified the essences, principles, methods and problems associated with the research of economic transformation and introduction of institutional reforms in the management systems of the company. The importance of the development of internal and external institutional environment is substantiated. Directions of development and reforming of enterprises to solve the identified problems are proposed.

Key words: institutional changes, enterprise problems, enterprise functions, enterprise reforms, competitiveness, organisational innovations, enterprise management systems, economic transformation.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada O'zbekiston milliy iqtisodiyotini o'zgartirish sharoitida korxonalar faoliyatining asosiy muammolari ko'rib chiqiladi. Kompaniyadagi bajaradigan funktsiyalar aniqlanadi. Muallif iqtisodiyotni o'zgartirish va kompaniyaning boshqaruv tizimlarida institutsional islohotlarni joriy etish bo'yicha tadqiqotlar o'tkazish bilan bog'liq mohiyat, printsiplar, usullar va muammolarni aniqladi. Ichki va tashqi institutsional muhitni rivojlantirishning ahamiyati asoslanadi. Belgilangan muammolarni hal qilish uchun korxonalarni rivojlantirish va isloh qilish yo'nalishlari taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: institutsional o'zgarishlar, korxonalar muammolari, korxonalar funktsiyalari, korxonalarni isloh qilish, raqobatbardoshlik, tashkiliy innovatsiyalar, korxonalarni boshqarish tizimlari, iqtisodiyotni o'zgartirish.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются основные проблемы функционирования предприятий в условиях трансформации национальной экономики Узбекистана. Определены функции, выполняемые предприятиями в обществе. Автор выявил сущности, принципы, методы и проблемы, связанные с проведением исследований трансформации экономики и внедрения институциональных реформ в системы менеджмента компании. Обоснована важность развития внутренней и внешней институциональной среды. Предложены направления развития и реформирования предприятий для решения выявленных проблем.

Ключевые слова: институциональные изменения, проблемы предприятий, функции предприятий, реформирование предприятий, конкурентоспособность, организационные инновации, системы управления предприятий, трансформация экономики.

INTRODUCTION

Today, against the backdrop of global changes in production and social structure, continuous development is a key element of successful management. This implies the need for research that can help to identify the main directions and opportunities for this development, as well as to explore alternative paths and innovations in the light of the green economy [1, 4, 7]. The evolution of management approaches in companies, the wealth of experience and knowledge of management professionals in the last decades plays a crucial role in ensuring the success of companies. In fact, company performance depends on many factors and idealising the role of management and its contribution to the global success of a company becomes a challenging task to assess its contribution [5, 8]. One of the most important aspects of the study of modern business structures is the collection and analysis of information that reflects the current state and dynamics of the company. A clear understanding of the different areas of the organisation's activities allows identifying key areas for further activities and making important management decisions in the context of the green economy.

DISCUSSIONS

For the successful fulfilment of tasks, it is important to implement a deep optimisation of the functioning of enterprises, with a special emphasis on improvement regarding the quality management system. This indicator plays a key role in the country's economy and its productive improvement contributes to GDP growth, consumer satisfaction and inflation reduction. Implementation of the current version of the international standard ISO 9001:2015 at large enterprises of Uzbekistan, including such companies as JSC "Uzbekistan Temir Yollari", JSC "Navoiyazot", JSC "Almalyk MMC", testifies to their impetus to the use of modern strategies and management methods, including quality management systems, taking into account the principles of "green economy". Over the last three years, these companies have obtained the following certificates: "ISO 9001:2015 - Quality Management System", "ISO 14001:2015 - Environmental Management System", "ISO 45001:2018 - Occupational Health and Safety Management System" and "ISO 50001:

For the first half of 2023 alone, over 610 enterprises in Uzbekistan have been certified in the Quality Management System: including

- 261 - Quality Management Systems (ISO 9001);
- 158- Environmental Management Systems (ISO 14001);
- 24 - food safety management systems (ISO 22000);
- 3- Energy management systems (ISO 50001);
- 164- professional systems, health care systems;
- 19- management systems within the framework of safety management (ISO 45001).

As of 1 July 2023, the State Register of Certified Quality Management Systems (QMS) of the Republic of Uzbekistan lists 10,582 enterprises and organisations that have successfully passed certification and confirmed compliance with international standards. Including ISO 9001-10104, ISO 14001 - 201, OHSAS 18001 - 256, ISO 22000 - 289, ISO/TS 45 (quality assurance of supplied parts in the automotive industry - 43 and GMP - 23. That is, quality management systems of domestic enterprises are mainly built on the basis of ISO 9000 International Standards, although there are other models of quality management systems. Despite significant financial investments and government support, quality management systems in many firms often fail to meet expectations. The main problem is related to the fact that the main goal of standardisation - guaranteeing high quality of goods and services, as well as the development of the enterprise and the management system as a whole - is often not achieved. The majority of experts specialising in assessing the quality of management in Uzavtosanoat JSC, including production managers, quality specialists and quality systems, believe that the effectiveness of quality management systems is less than expected. The effectiveness of the quality management process, as well as the results of departments and groups responsible for quality management systems, are poorly correlated with overall quality indicators. The ambiguities that lead to this situation are many, and the most significant ones, in our opinion, are the following:

1. **Organisational issues:** One of the main reasons is the separation of individual quality units from quality management systems (QMS). This simplifies the processes of QMS creation and certification, at the same time it leads to weakened efficiency in quality assurance as QMS becomes a goal in itself, detached from the core business processes^[3].
2. **Administrative factors:** another reason is the weak linkage of QMS performance indicators to the overall strategy and control of the enterprise. Lack of proper coordination with other management units leads to unproductive quality control.
3. **Insufficient training of QMS employees:** Neither the level of training of QMS unit employees in the administration of production processes nor their limited authority may limit their ability to control the quality of the final product.
4. **Incomplete levels of management development in the enterprise:** Another reason may be the lack of experts capable of dealing with highly specialised issues, including issues in product and process quality assurance.

These factors significantly affect the effectiveness of quality management systems and require careful consideration by the company's management to address them and improve the overall level of product and process quality. Most of the above issues are fairly formalised, i.e. their nature, causes, development factors are well known. However, the solution of these complex issues requires fundamental research at a high scientific and methodological level, as they have a significant impact on modern enterprise management.

Organisation and stimulation of personnel innovation activities in the field of product quality improvement and process optimisation is one of the critical elements of quality management and an integral aspect of modern enterprise management. Japanese companies have made significant progress in ensuring product quality through the creative approach of their employees to the work process. For example, each employee of Japanese automotive companies offers an average of 61.6 process improvements per year, compared to only 0.4 in Europe. In this connection, European and American researchers and practitioners of quality management are actively studying, mastering, adapting and developing methods of involving employees in product quality management and company development, as well as forming a creative attitude to the work process. Research into the quality management approaches and tools of Japanese enterprises has received considerable investment and has led to great results. For example, Kaizen's improvement suggestion scores were 4.2 for the US and 1.9 for European car plants. Involvement of employees in the process of product quality improvement and expansion of technical creativity of employees is of particular importance at the enterprises of Uzavtosanoat JSC, especially at UzAuto Motors JSC, JV LLC "Samarkand Automobile Plant" and JV LLC "UZ TRUCK AND BUS MOTORS".

The example of UzAuto Motors JSC shows that since 2000 the enterprise has been developing a system of proposals to improve production, similar to the system of rationalisation proposals used by foreign partners. From 2000 to 2022, the number of submitted rationalisation proposals increased significantly - from 402 to 15,103, and the specific index of submission of rationalisation proposals per employee increased from 0.12 to 3.11. This indicates a significant increase in the activity of employees in proposing improvements.

The ratio of rationalisation proposals (the ratio of implemented proposals to the total number of submitted proposals) also increased significantly, indicating that employees' proposals are actively used in the production process. The ratio of realised to submitted proposals increased from 35.1% to 66%, indicating a more efficient use of proposals within the company's operations. An important achievement is also the increase in employee participation in rationalisation, which is reflected in the engagement ratio. Employee involvement in process improvement has increased from 3% in 2000 to 82.7% in 2022. This indicates that most employees are actively involved in product and process improvement, which contributes to the overall success of the company.

However, behind the history of rationalisation and innovation in the enterprise is a slowdown and stagnation. This is evident both in the decline in the number of submitted rationalisation proposals at work sites and locations and in the reduction of some innovation programmes.

A detailed analysis of innovation in the enterprise indicates problems of rationalisation development, such as formality and over-management, a large number of insignificant proposals submitted formally rather than for the sake of real improvement. In order to assess more accurately the state of rationalisation and to identify ways to improve it, surveys were conducted among the participants in the rationalisation movement of all types of employees. Special attention was paid to the following aspects of rationalisation activity: Motivation for participation, i.e. the reasons that encourage workers to take part in the rationalisation movement. Key motivations were improved working conditions and rewards for employees and colleagues. Activity drivers, which are the reasons why workers are active in presenting innovative ideas. These include initiative, innovativeness and supervisor demands. Systematic factors affecting the effectiveness of innovation activities. These include production and management culture, production climate, support or obstacles from management. The analysis of these factors makes it possible to identify the real difficulties and problems faced by the participants of the rationalisation movement and to select solutions for further improvement of the rationalisation system and innovation activity at the enterprise.

CONCLUSION

The current economic situation in the marketplace requires organisations to constantly adapt and metamorphose to maintain their competitive position. Effective reform both in technological and organisational plans becomes a critical factor for successful operation of business structures.

Organisational innovations play a major role in the processes of economic transformation and institutional restructuring. They serve as a basis for the creation and implementation of new concepts of enterprise management, which allows successfully adapting to continuous changes in the market environment.

One of the important aspects discussed in this article is the study of enterprise management systems as socio-technical systems. This makes it possible to understand at a deeper level the characteristics and dynamics of modern, rapidly evolving organisations and to identify areas for their improvement. Conducting research on the transformation of the economy and on the introduction of institutional changes in enterprise management systems requires thorough and comprehensive preparation. A scientific and methodological approach to research plays a key role in achieving positive dynamics and introducing innovative approaches to enterprise management.

Taking into account the ever-changing market conditions and business requirements, conducting in-depth research is becoming an integral part of the work of companies that seek to remain competitive and successful. It also contributes to improving the quality of management in enterprises and ensures their stable development in a variable economic market.

Thus, the raised problems and research methods can become a starting point for further elaborations and practical actions in the field of enterprise management taking into account the challenges and future prospects for the modern economy.

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Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Xondamir Ismoilov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2023. № 10

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"Yashil iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot”
jurnali

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta’lim, fan va innovatsiyalar
vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy
attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-
sonli qarori bilan ro‘yxatdan
o‘tkazilgan.